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D4.4 Training report

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Abstract

This training report details the capacity-building activities organised by the SUBMERSE project to bridge knowledge gaps in using submarine fibre-optic cables as environmental sensing infrastructure. It outlines a strategic methodology based on training needs mapping that resulted in specialised learning paths for research scientists, optical engineers, and data stewards. The document summarises the implementation of live training sessions and the creation of open-access online resources designed to ensure the long-term sustainability of project outcomes within the global scientific community.

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Executive Summary

The SUBMERSE project explores a transformative approach to ocean monitoring by utilising existing submarine telecommunication fibre-optic cables as large-scale sensing infrastructure. By acquiring optical signals through Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) and State of Polarisation (SOP) sensing, the project addresses critical gaps in geophysical and oceanographic monitoring. However, the successful exploitation of these technologies requires specific technical expertise and standardised workflows. This report summarises the activities of Task 4.3, Capacity-building and Training, which was dedicated to developing the skills necessary to collect, interpret, and process data generated by SUBMERSE instrumentation.

The project's training strategy was built upon a rigorous training needs assessment conducted in 2024. This assessment involved interviewing task leaders and project partners to identify strategic priorities and challenges. By aligning these needs with the broader SUBMERSE engagement strategy, the project identified three primary learning paths:

- 1) **Infrastructure** reproducibility and sustainability, focused on guidance for technicians and network providers regarding device interoperability and data handling.
- 2) **Data Lifecycle Management**, focused on (meta)data management and FAIR-compliant workflows for scientists and data stewards.
- 3) **Scientific Applications**, focused on training geoscientists, oceanographers, and marine biologists on how to analyse high-volume DAS and complex SOP data.

Training delivery followed a "live-first" approach, where interactive sessions were later converted into asynchronous online resources. To facilitate this, SUBMERSE utilised Google Colab as a cloud-based teaching platform, allowing participants to easily access real datasets in a reproducible Python-based environment. Long-term accessibility is guaranteed through the LifeWatch ERIC training platform, which hosts the project's learning resources using a Moodle-based Learning Management System.

Between December 2024 and April 2026, SUBMERSE delivered six key training activities: a) an internal capacity-building webinar on SOP analysis for seismic monitoring (December 2024); b) two public sessions at the IASPEI Early Career Scientists School in Lisbon (August 2025), covering DAS fundamentals and SOP data analysis; c) three specialised sessions during the SUBMERSE Community Event in Copenhagen (April 2026), focusing on deep learning for earthquake detection, oceanographic and marine biology applications, and the Madeira Island GeoLab fibre.

Evaluation of these activities revealed a high demand for hands-on practice and mathematical fundamentals associated with SOP data. Despite the remaining gaps, the training provision successfully demonstrated how fibre-optic sensing can provide critical solutions to unsolved problems in ocean monitoring, such as coastal wave identification.

The report concludes that while SUBMERSE has made significant progress in overcoming operational barriers, e.g., managing high-volume DAS data and SOP signal interpretation, further training is required. Recommendations include expanding technical training for infrastructure replication, promoting open science and cloud-based computing practices, and increasing strategic awareness among policymakers regarding data governance and infrastructure security.

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope and purpose of the training report

This training report provides an overview of the training activities organised by SUBMERSE Task 4.3 Capacity-building and Training. The overall objective of this task was to develop knowledge and skills required to successfully collect, interpret, process and reuse data generated by the SUBMERSE instrumentation.

The SUBMERSE project explored the use of submarine telecommunication fibre-optic cables as a large-scale environmental sensing infrastructure. By exploiting optical signals travelling through existing submarine networks across vast oceanic regions, the project investigated two complementary sensing approaches: Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) and State of Polarisation (SOP) sensing. These technologies were chosen for their potential to fill gaps in the current approaches to geophysical and oceanographic phenomena monitoring, without the need for new, dedicated submarine instrumentation.

While experimental results demonstrate the considerable scientific potential of fibre sensing technologies, the SUBMERSE project also highlighted several knowledge gaps and operational challenges that this task contributed to addressing.

1.2 Structure of the document

This deliverable is organised into five chapters and a supporting appendix to provide a comprehensive overview of the SUBMERSE training strategy against its outcomes.

Chapter 1: Introduction provides the scope of the report. It outlines the purpose of the training task as part of the broader project's goal to exploit submarine cables for environmental sensing via DAS and SOP technologies.

Chapter 2: Training Needs Assessment details the methodology used to design the training plan. It explains the process of training needs mapping, which involved stakeholder interviews and the definition of learning objectives. This chapter also introduces the three core learning paths (Infrastructure, Data Management, and Scientific Applications) that guided the project's educational output.

Chapter 3: Training Content Production and Dissemination describes the rationale behind the selected delivery modes and tools. It explains the "live-first" delivery strategy and the use of Google Colab for interactive scientific tutorials. Furthermore, it details how LifeWatch ERIC training infrastructure supported SUBMERSE, providing the primary repository for project training resources.

Chapter 4: Training Activities offers a detailed account of the capacity-building and public training sessions conducted throughout the project. It includes specific data on participant demographics, trainer panels, and learning objectives for each session, as well as an analysis of impact based on pre- and post-training feedback.

Chapter 5: Conclusion and Recommendations synthesise the lessons learned. It addresses the operational barriers overcome during the project while also proposing future training areas to accelerate the adoption of fibre-optic sensing, specifically in the realms of Open Science, cloud computing, and policy-level strategic awareness.

The document concludes with Appendix A, which provides a complete mapping of training needs, strategic priorities, and target beneficiaries, followed by a list of References and a Glossary of technical terms.

2 Training needs assessment

2.1 Methodology

The training activities delivered by SUBMERSE partners were planned following an assessment of strategic priorities and training needs across all the Working Packages (WPs). A training needs assessment is the process of collecting data about organisational and individual needs that may be satisfied by a relevant and timely training provision. It is worth considering that not all needs can be addressed by training actions. A training need corresponds to an existing gap between the current level and type of knowledge, skills, mindset, and practices and the desired one (Barbazette, 2006). An effective training needs assessment should be conducted according to the time and resources available, and with specific organisational structure and goals in mind.

The methodology adopted for the training needs assessment followed a combined approach of: 1) a training needs mapping and 2) alignment with the SUBMERSE engagement strategy.

Training needs mapping | The initial training needs analysis was conducted in 2024 by directly interviewing task leaders in WP2 and WP3 in one-to-one conversations and during project meetings. Project partners were invited to reflect on their strategic priorities in terms of needs, gaps, and target groups. These priorities were then elaborated into a preliminary list of learning objectives, required prior knowledge and skills, and relevant training content activities, which, in turn, were organised into possible learning paths. Establishing specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound learning objectives is the foundational step to designing a transformative learning experience (Kratwohl, D. R., 2022). Moreover, training activities and content can be organised in thematic and narrative-based learning paths, through which the level of required competency gradually increases. The training needs mapping was iteratively revised and improved based on progress of, and insights from, the project's scientific and technical deliverables.

Alignment with engagement strategy | Since every training activity provides a valuable opportunity to connect with stakeholders, the training plan was aligned with the project's engagement strategy. The SUBMERSE training targeted the primary groups of stakeholders identified in D4.2, Stakeholder engagement and outreach plan, namely, project participants, partner organisations, research and user communities, and the technology side.

2.2 Findings

Building on the assessment of strategic priorities, challenges, and training needs, three learning paths were identified:

- 1) **Infrastructure reproducibility and sustainability**, including technology interoperability, location constraints, and handling of sensitive data. This learning path serves use case scientists, technicians, developers, submarine cable vendors, and network providers who require detailed technical guidance.
- 2) **Data Lifecycle Management**, providing training in (meta)data management and FAIR-compliant workflows to scientists and data stewards for a better integration with research infrastructures and data providers.
- 3) **Scientific Applications**, providing the geosciences, oceanography, and marine biology communities with instruction and educational tools on how to access, interpret, analyse and store high-volume DAS and complex SOP data.

A complete overview of the training needs mapping is provided in **Appendix A**.

3 Training content production and dissemination

3.1 Format and delivery mode

Format and delivery mode of the training activities were calibrated on the learning needs, previous knowledge, and level of autonomy of the target beneficiaries.

A live-first delivery mode was consistently adopted, followed by the production of online training resources, freely and asynchronously accessible. For advanced scientists, engineers, and developers, both online and on-site training delivery was chosen. For early-career scientists, training was provided exclusively on-site to ensure proper assistance with the Python-based coursework and an effective trainer-to-trainee ratio. Three training formats were implemented: on-demand online capacity-building sessions, on-site training sessions as part of a broader summer school programme, and on-site training sessions as a core element of the SUBMERSE Community Event.

3.2 Monitoring and evaluation

In preparation for the training sessions dedicated to early-career scientists, a pre-training assessment (<https://zfrmz.eu/AVQtIQwEaTY8Q0Sq8mHI>) was administered to collect: 1) participants' profiles, and demographics; 2) technical proficiency with Python and Jupyter Notebooks; 3) their self-evaluation of the ability to perform specific tasks related to DAS and SOP applications in their research field, and 4) personal expectations and motivation to join the summer school. Participants' feedback about each training session was organically collected by the summer school host organisation and shared with the SUBMERSE project partners. The pre-training survey findings and the post-training feedback are summarised under paragraph 4.2, "Detailed account" of chapter 4, "Training activities".

3.3 Software and platforms

3.3.1 Google Colab

Google Colaboratory (Colab) was chosen as the cloud-based teaching platform for the live scientific tutorials that required access and processing of SOP and DAS real datasets. All exercises were executed and shared in Google Colab, ensuring a reproducible environment.

Google Colab is a pre-configured, in-browser Python-based platform, modelled after Jupyter Notebooks. The Colab approach presents significant advantages both for learners and for trainers in terms of accessibility, interoperability, and cognitive load. Google Colab was preferred over alternatives since it requires no local installation of Python or server configuration, with minimal device-specific troubleshooting for students, who can customise the notebook by manually installing additional dependencies. Google Colab, and similar solutions, are widely adopted across the SUBMERSE scientific communities, who appreciate the possibility of including and modifying code blocks and narrative text directly through the Colab user interface, allowing for easy exploration and documentation of scientific workflows. While constraints exist, such as computational limitations for the free version and the need for an internet connection, the benefits of Google Colab outweigh its disadvantages in the context of the SUBMERSE training provision.

3.3.2 LifeWatch ERIC training platform

The SUBMERSE project has placed strong emphasis on building comprehensive training materials that support the diverse groups involved in the development, operation, and scientific exploitation of submarine DAS and SOP data. LifeWatch ERIC, using its established training platform, hosts the SUBMERSE training resources and ensures long-term accessibility under the section “International Projects/SUBMERSE”: <https://training.lifewatch.eu/en/categories/international-projects/submerse/>

The LifeWatch ERIC training platform combines the flexibility of a widely used Content Management System as WordPress, with the full-featured Learning Management System Moodle. Moodle is an open-source software package designed to produce, manage, and analyse personalised learning resources. The tagging system of Moodle allows for an advanced search via a customisable set of filters, according to the relevant target audience, learning objectives, and format. The metadata of each learning resource is collected by LifeWatch in a metadata catalogue in compliance with the FAIR practices of the IEEE Standard for Learning Object Metadata and the EOSC Training Resource Profile - Data Model.

3.3.3 SUBMERSE project website

Access to the SUBMERSE training resources is possible from the SUBMERSE project website, with a page dedicated to training: submerse.eu/training

Figure 1: SUBMERSE project website – training page

4 Training activities

4.1 Overview

The SUBMERSE training provision aimed to promote close collaboration and alignment between the technology side of fibre-optic development and its scientific applications. In total, one capacity-building session and five training sessions were delivered between December 2024 and April 2026, including:

- Internal capacity-building webinar on State of Polarisation (SOP) analysis, held in December 2024 by subject matter experts coming from both industry and academia;
- Two training sessions, respectively dedicated to DAS and SOP data, were delivered by SUBMERSE project partners in August 2025, during the last day of the IASPEI (International Association of Seismology and Physics of the Earth's Interior) School, dedicated to early-career scientists: <https://iaga-iaspei-2025.org/early-career-school/>. The education programme was conveniently scheduled a week before the IAGA/IASPEI Joint Scientific Meeting 2025, where SUBMERSE was present with a booth together with EMSO, EPOS and the Geo-INQUIRE project.
- Three training sessions delivered by SUBMERSE project partners, covering all use cases, at the SUBMERSE Community Event in April 2026.

For each training activity, at least one online training resource was produced for a total of six, meeting WP4 - KPI4.4 : Number of training courses by the end of the project (≥ 3).

4.2 Detailed account

INTERNAL CAPACITY-BUILDING SESSION	
Title	Introduction to State of Polarisation analysis: the example of seismic monitoring
Date and location	06 December 2024, online
Format	Online lecture and tutorials – 2 hours
Scope	This training session introduced SUBMERSE partners and invitees to data recording, measurement, and analysis methods of State of Polarisation (SOP) in optical networks. It provided technical insights into SOP and its relation to sensing on deployed fibre cables.
Target beneficiaries	Project partners and project organisations: cable technicians, dev ops, optical engineers; advanced use case scientists.
Trainer panel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kurosh Bozorgebrahimi, Senior Advisor for Optical Networks at Sikt • Benjamin Koch, Research Associate at Universität Paderborn / Novoptel GmbH • Kristina Skarvang Vaskinn, PhD candidate at NTNU Centre for Geophysical Forecasting
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define State of Polarisation through key correlated concepts and models of visualisation; • List causes and effects of polarisation changes;

INTERNAL CAPACITY-BUILDING SESSION	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe different types of SOP measurement methods, with respective limitations; • Recognise recording types with PM1000; • Analyse SOP data using MATLAB; • Explain benefits of using both Full-Stokes and PBS-based polarimeters for earthquake monitoring.
Strategic priorities	Advanced site setup: DAS and SOP Integration; Handling sensitive data; Geosciences use cases
Impact	This webinar supported 52 participants from both WP2 and WP3 with the implementation and validation of sensing devices in the SUBMERSE project.
Public link	https://training.lifewatch.eu/en/categories/international-projects/submerse/resource/Intro_SOP_data_analysis/

Table 1: Internal capacity-building session

PUBLIC TRAINING SESSION #1	
Title	DAS fundamentals and DAS data management
Date and location	29 August 2025, Lisbon, hosted by IASPEI Early Career Scientists School 2025
Format	On-site lectures and exercises – 2 hours
Scope	This training session focused on the practical fundamentals of Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) and on data management policies standardisation for DAS in seismology. Participants were guided in hands-on exercises to perform metadata validation using structured JSON schemas, access large cloud storage to stream data directly into a Python environment, and evaluate different data formats.
Target beneficiaries	Early-career use case scientists; data stewards; cable technicians.
Trainer panel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr. Afonso Loureiro, Researcher at ARDITI / Instituto Dom Luiz • Dr. Javier Quinteros, Researcher and GEOFON Data Centre Manager at GFZ
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe the physics of Rayleigh backscattering that allows fibre-optic cables to act as seismic sensors; • Navigate cloud storages to programmatically retrieve seismic datasets; • Implement workflows to optimise memory usage; • Validate and interpret JSON metadata to ensure that seafloor cable coordinates are correct.
Strategic priorities	Advanced site setup: DAS and SOP Integration; Enabling FAIRness; Geosciences use cases.

PUBLIC TRAINING SESSION #1	
Impact	<p>Before this training session, the international group of 37 early-career scientists, including mostly Master’s graduates and early-stage PhDs, were asked to rate their confidence in performing specific tasks related to DAS data. With 24 replies received, we could see that participants felt moderately confident in defining applications for DAS, but struggled with converting HDF5 data, data visualisation, identifying acquisition parameters, and estimating storage requirements.</p> <p>Based on the feedback provided by 18 students after the training session, many found the content new, interesting, and promising for future research. However, some described the session as too brief with limited time for exercises. More extensive hands-on practice with additional tutorials, real data samples and study cases were requested. The metadata section was highlighted as especially useful.</p>
Public link	https://training.lifewatch.eu/en/categories/international-projects/submerse/resource/intro_to_DAS_data/

Table 2: Public training session #1

PUBLIC TRAINING SESSION #2	
Title	A practical introduction to State of Polarisation (SOP) data analysis
Date and location	29 August 2025, Lisbon, hosted by IASPEI Early Career Scientists School 2025
Format	On-site lectures and exercises – 2 hours
Scope	<p>The session introduced participants to a novel approach to seismological research, using State of Polarisation (SOP) data and Python language. The first part of the training session covered the basic theoretical principles needed to analyse in Python language large numerical datasets. In the second half of the session, participants discovered how to access and visualise SOP generated data. For this exercise, a pre-checked HDF5 dataset containing both real and artificially induced data was provided. Participants worked on a pre-prepared Colab notebook to perform analysis of the provided data.</p>
Target beneficiaries	Early-career use case scientists.
Trainer panel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ing. Rudolf Vohnout, Ph.D., Researcher at CESNET • Ing. Martin Šlapák, Ph.D., Researcher at CESNET
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Define State of Polarisation and Stokes parameters; • Calculate the rate of SOP change using Python; • Apply standard seismic filters to optical data to extract coherent seismic phases; • Discuss the value of SOP applications in combination with DAS-based methods on a global submarine fibre-optic network for ocean monitoring.
Strategic priorities	Advanced site setup: DAS and SOP Integration; Geosciences use cases.

PUBLIC TRAINING SESSION #2	
Impact	<p>Before the training session, 24 out of 37 early-career scientists expressed a significantly lower familiarity with SOP than with DAS. Most participants reported to feeling "Not at all" or "Hardly" confident for all SOP-related tasks, indicating this was a completely new topic for most of them. However, expectations were high for hands-on exercises, particularly about learning how to integrate these technologies into current research.</p> <p>Based on the post-training feedback provided by 18 students, the SOP training session was received as somewhat unclear. Considering the novelty and complexity of the mathematical transformation of optical data into a format that seismologists can interpret, it was requested to expand in the near future time for both SOP theory and practical applications, especially by Python beginners. Participants also requested resource sharing for future reference, including scripts, instructions, and datasets.</p>
Public link	https://training.lifewatch.eu/en/categories/international-projects/submerse/resource/practical_intro_SOP_data_analysis/

Table 3: Public training session #2

PUBLIC TRAINING SESSION #3	
Title	Madeira Island site: the GeoLab Fibre
Date and location	15 April 2026, Copenhagen, SUBMERSE Community Event
Format	On-site tutorial – 40 minutes
Scope	The session explored the scientific potential of a 57-kilometer dark fibre around Madeira, branching off the main cable connecting Brazil and Portugal. Using an OptoDAS interrogator, GeoLab researchers have been collecting data since 2023 at a 500 Hz sampling rate and 10m gauge length. For the practical part of the session, a real sample dataset from October 2023 was downloaded for running a guided analysis on a prepared Colab notebook.
Target beneficiaries	Advanced use case scientists; cable technicians; optical engineers.
Trainer panel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr. Afonso Loureiro, Researcher at ARDITI / Instituto Dom Luiz
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stream submarine DAS data directly into a notebook; • Convert optical measurements to strain metrics; • Use Frequency-Wavenumber (FK) filters to isolate signals; • Use template matching to track marine mammals; • Apply wave dispersion analysis to understand shallow-water dynamics.
Strategic priorities	Advanced site setup: DAS and SOP Integration; Oceanography use cases; Marine Biology use cases; Interdisciplinary use cases.

PUBLIC TRAINING SESSION #3	
Impact	The workshop, open to both project partners and external stakeholders, demonstrated how a fibre cable, originally intended for engineering purposes, can detect biological signals (whales) and oceanographic phenomena (surface waves). Participants successfully pulled manageable DAS records from a remote S3 bucket.
Public link	https://training.lifewatch.eu/en/categories/international-projects/submerse/resource/Madeira_Island_site_GeoLab_fibre/

Table 4: Public training session #3

PUBLIC TRAINING SESSION #4	
Title	Picking DAS records with deep learning: DeepSubDAS and the SeisBench DAS interface
Date and location	15 April 2026, Copenhagen, SUBMERSE Community Event
Format	On-site lecture and tutorial – 30 minutes
Scope	This training session focused on the application of Deep Learning for automated earthquake detection on Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS) records. The practical tutorial demonstrated how the SeisBench library can help process the complex, high-volume DAS data produced by submarine cables, with the DAS-native model DeepSubDAS applied to an earthquake record used as example.
Target beneficiaries	Advanced use case scientists; cable technicians; optical engineers.
Trainer panel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Jannes Münchmeyer, Postdoctoral researcher at GFZ
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify seismic waveforms (phase picking); Programmatically access global seismic benchmark datasets using the SeisBench standardised API; Apply deep learning models as DeepSubDAS to process and analyse data originating from submarine fibre optic cables in (a) single channel mode, (b) multi-channel mode.
Strategic priorities	Enabling FAIRness; Geosciences use cases.
Impact	The training session successfully demonstrated how machine learning can help in automation of geosciences tasks, as picking of earthquake arrivals in seconds, and how the SeisBench framework can standardise workflows for ML seismology, regardless of the different data formats.
Public link	https://training.lifewatch.eu/en/categories/international-projects/submerse/resource/Picking_DAS_records_with_deep_learning

Table 5: Public training session #4

PUBLIC TRAINING SESSION #5	
Title	Fibre optics for Oceanographic Applications
Date and location	15 April 2026, Copenhagen, SUBMERSE Community Event
Format	On-site lecture and tutorial – 45 minutes
Scope	The training session focused on the visualisation and preliminary processing of DAS data for oceanographic applications. The trainers demonstrated how to handle high-volume DAS records by using a downsampled dataset from the GeoLab fibre in Madeira. Participants were provided a prepared workflow in Colab to familiarise themselves with how signals change along different segments of a submarine cable, moving from land and the narrow shelf into deep water.
Target beneficiaries	Advanced use case scientists; cable technicians; optical engineers.
Trainer panel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aggeliki Barberopoulou, Research Scientist at HCMR • Athanasia Papapostolou, Research Associate at HCMR
Learning objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognise content of DAS files in both time and frequency domains; • Explain how depth and location (e.g., land vs. sea) influence signals recorded by fibre-optic cables; • Downsample data to isolate oceanographic waves from high-frequency acoustic noise; • Apply standard seismic processing tools to non-traditional submarine sensor data.
Strategic priorities	Enabling FAIRness; Oceanography use cases; Geosciences use cases.
Impact	The training session demonstrated how fibre optic sensing can also be a high-fidelity tool for physical oceanography. By the end the SUBMERSE Community Event, 45 participants could identify specific frequency of coastal waves from raw fibre signals. This application aims to fill critical gaps in ocean observing and monitoring.
Public link	https://training.lifewatch.eu/en/categories/international-projects/submerse/resource/Fibre_optics_Oceanographic_Applications

Table 6: Public training session #5

5 Conclusion

With its learning paths, SUBMERSE contributed to sharing knowledge and overcoming key operational barriers in the exploitation of DAS and SOP-based network sensing, including: a large volume of DAS data, processing and archiving complexity, and a lack of standardisation for consistent integration of DAS records across research infrastructures and data providers. The SUBMERSE training provision also tackled SOP device heterogeneity, signal interpretation complexity, and a limited validation of datasets, being SOP an emerging approach to seafloor data analysis.

5.1 Recommendations

Fibre optic sensing represents a transformative opportunity for ocean and environmental monitoring. However, realising the full potential of these technologies requires addressing a series of standing scientific, technical, and governance challenges. Further training opportunities are therefore expected in the following areas:

1. **Technical training** to accelerate and replicate sensing infrastructure design, set-up, implementation and maintenance, the overall scope being to determine what instrumentation to install or re-purpose and meet global scientific goals;
2. **Training on open science, data management and research software.** Cloud-based computing is slowly democratising the ability to conduct complex analyses of earth science datasets, creating new room for transparency and reproducibility. However, working with new data formats may require not only powerful cloud computing facilities, but also a shift in scientific practises;
3. **Strategic awareness raising for and capacity building directed to policymakers** to evaluate, design and implement the most fitting trusted research environment approach for national security and data governance challenges.

Appendix A SUBMERSE Training needs mapping

Learning path	Strategic Priority	Training needs	Target beneficiaries	Preliminary knowledge	Training content
Infrastructure reproducibility and sustainability	Advanced site setup: DAS and SOP Integration	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Deploy DAS and SOP in same location: install time and frequency services at interrogator sites with DAS and SOP; 2) Ensure data outputs are synchronised and integrated; 3) Set up data transmission to secure storage. 	National coordinators, technicians, optical engineers.	Optical networking, cloud compute management, IP routing, DevOps, Software development (Python/MATLAB).	Interoperability between DAS sensing and telecom, DAS and SOP data integration, time stamping, data processing, signal processing, hardware requirements.
Infrastructure reproducibility and sustainability	Handling sensitive data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Basic recognition of signals received by DAS and SOP; 2) Basic signal analysis and identification (whale, earthquake, vessel, wave); 3) Coordinate communications with authorities, data 	Managers, National coordinators, technicians.	Software development (Python/MATLAB), signals analysis, cloud management, DevOps.	Checking and scrubbing sensitive data, develop software for automatic detection of sensitive data.

Learning path	Strategic Priority	Training needs	Target beneficiaries	Preliminary knowledge	Training content
		<p>handling and storage in secure environment;</p> <p>4) Managing clearance procedure for data.</p>			
Data lifecycle management	Enabling FAIRness	<p>1) Set up ontology for national fibre sensing or ontology for a specific site, enabling PID minting on open data;</p> <p>2) Ensuring buffer to maintain archive relationship.</p>	Scientists, National coordinators, technicians, data stewards.	Software development (Python), open science awareness, Webprotégé	PID and FAIRness, DAS data management strategy, data validation, datasets development, and publication.
Scientific applications	Geoscience use cases	<p>1) Access, process, and interpret data;</p> <p>2) Identify earthquakes.</p>	Scientists, National coordinators, technicians.	Basic software coding (Python/MATLAB), signals analysis.	Real time earthquake monitoring, machine learning for DAS analysis.
Scientific applications	Oceanography use cases	<p>1) Access, process, and interpret data;</p> <p>2) Identify wave families.</p>	Scientists, National coordinators, technicians.	Basic software coding (Python/MATLAB), signals analysis	Oceanographic analysis
Scientific applications	Marine Biology use cases	<p>1) Access, process, and interpret data;</p> <p>2) Identify whale song.</p>	Scientists, National coordinators, technicians.	Basic software coding (Python/MATLAB), signals analysis	Baleen Whale spotting

Learning path	Strategic Priority	Training needs	Target beneficiaries	Preliminary knowledge	Training content
Scientific applications	Interdisciplinary use cases	1) Access, process, and interpret data across use cases.	Scientists, National coordinators, technicians.	Basic software coding (Python/MATLAB), signals analysis.	Calibration of experiments and cross-comparison.

Table A.1: Training needs mapping

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Glossary

API	Application Programming Interface
ARDITI	Regional Agency for the Development of Research, Technology, and Innovation
CESNET	Czech Education and Scientific NETwork
DAS	Distributed Acoustic Sensing
EMSO	European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and Water Column Observatory
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EPOS	European Plate Observing System
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FK	Frequency-Wavenumber
GEOFON	GEO Research Network
GFZ	German Research Centre for Geosciences
HDF5	Hierarchical Data Format version 5
IAGA	International Association of Geomagnetism and Aeronomy
IASPEI	International Association of Seismology and Physics of the Earth's Interior
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine learning
PBS	Polarising Beam Splitter
PID	Persistent Identifier
S3	Simple Storage Service
SOP	State of Polarisation
WP	Work Package